

Building the Legal Knowledge Graph for Smart Compliance Services in Multilingual Europe

D5.4 Testing and evaluation plan

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ACRONYMS LIST

DBMS	Database Management System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
JWT	Json Web Token
LKG	Legal Knowledge Graph
QADOC	Question and Answering System
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this document is to describe the testing and evaluation plan of the Lynx platform, which is organized in three different levels: microservice level, integration level, and pilot use case level.

In the microservice level the Lynx microservices are tested as single components. The evaluation methodology of this level is discussed and decided within WP3. Integration level testing aims to verify the functionalities of the Lynx platform implemented by many microservices that are integrated together. The population workflow, which is used to enrich documents and add them to the LKG, is clearly the functionality of this level that deserves more attention because of its complexity. The simpler test case of the population workflow consists of running a single instance of it, and, when it is completed, check whether the correctness conditions are satisfied. Moreover, to test the behaviour of the system under a stress condition, workloads of several population workflow instances will also be experimented.

The objective of pilot use case level testing is to verify the proper functioning of the Lynx platform from the customer perspective. With this purpose, use case testing will be experimented, a black box software testing technique in which the tester follows the steps defined by the use cases and verify that they work as expected.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
TABLE OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF TABLES.....	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
2 INTEGRATION LEVEL TESTING AND EVALUATION PLAN	9
2.1 TEST 1: PRIVATE COLLECTIONS	9
2.1.1 Test scenario	9
2.1.2 Data collection	10
2.1.3 Performance evaluation	10
2.2 TEST 2: POPULATION WORKFLOW	10
2.2.1 Test scenario	10
2.2.2 Data collection	10
2.2.3 Performance evaluation	11
3 PILOT USE CASES LEVEL TESTING AND EVALUATION PLAN	12
3.1 TEST STRATEGY	12
3.1.1 Data and Database Integrity Testing	12
3.1.2 Function Testing	12
3.1.3 User Interface Testing.....	13
3.1.4 Performance Testing.....	13
3.1.5 Security and Access Control Testing.....	14
3.2 OPENLAWS: CONTRACTS	15
3.2.1 Requirements for Test	15
3.3 DNV GL: GEOTHERMAL ENERGY	16
3.3.1 Requirements for Test	16
3.4 CUATRECASAS: LABOUR LAW	16
3.4.1 Requirements for Test	17

3.4.2	Acceptation criteria	18
4	CONCLUSIONS	20
	ANNEX: POPULATION WORKFLOW SPECIFICATION	21
	REST API	22
5	REFERENCES	23

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1 BPMN 2.0 diagram of the population workflow.....	21
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LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 A sample enrichment configuration	21
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1 INTRODUCTION

T5.4 *Testing and evaluation plan* started in November 2018 and is still ongoing. Its specific objective is the verification of the Lynx platform against the functional requirements gathered in T1.1 *Industry requirements elicitation* and T4.1 *Pilot Use Cases and Requirements Study*, and the non-functional requirements gathered in T1.2 *Technical requirements specification*.

The purpose of this document is to describe the testing and evaluation plan of the Lynx platform, which is organized in three different levels:

- **Microservice level:** Lynx microservices are tested as single components. The methodology and the evaluation measures are discussed and specified within WP3.
- **Integration level:** at this level, the functionalities of the Lynx platform, consisting of many microservices integrated together, are tested. A description of their testing and evaluation plan is presented in Section 2 of this document.
- **Pilot use-cases level:** this is the higher abstraction level, and its objective is to test the functioning of the Lynx platform from the customer perspective. Section 3 of this document describes the plan and methodology for testing and evaluating the pilot use cases.

2 INTEGRATION LEVEL TESTING AND EVALUATION PLAN

This section focuses on the testing and evaluation plan for the all the functionalities of the Lynx platform implemented by several microservices integrated together.

The platform level testing and evaluation plan is based on the “Test and Evaluation Master Plan” (TEMP) (Test and Evaluation Master Plan Guidebook.), which is a project evaluation methodology. TEMP consists of individual tests having each three parts:

- Test scenario: establishes specific test conditions. The test scenario identifies the following: items required for testing, instructions to set up the items that will be used during the test, general description for how to operate the system under test, and specific actions and events that will take place during the test.
- Data collection: identifies information what must be used and collected during the test. This includes: settings for the system under test, sample collection, the ability to extract and record specific kinds of data from the system while it is operating normally.
- Performance evaluation: analysis of the data after the testing is complete.
 - Measures of effectiveness are specific metrics that are used to measure results in the overall mission and execution of assigned tasks.
 - Measures of performance are specific metrics that have a pass or fail threshold that must be satisfied. These are generally identified with the words shall or must in the specification.
 - Measures of suitability evaluate the ability to be supported in its intended operational environment: Reliability, Availability, Maintainability, Supportability or Usability

The following sub-sections describe the particular tests designed for the project.

2.1 TEST 1: PRIVATE COLLECTIONS

This test aims to verify the confidentiality of private collections, which means that private collections should be accessible only by authorized users.

2.1.1 Test scenario

This test scenario covers all the ways of accessing Lynx collections that are exposed to the external clients, which are:

- “Get document” API of the Document Manager service.
- “Start population workflow instance” API of the Workflow Manager service.
- “Search” API of the Search service.
- “Get similar documents” API of the Semantic Similarity service.

The first step of this test scenario is using one of the OAuth 2.0 (IETF) grant types to retrieve a JSON Web Token (JWT). Then, for each of the API listed before, three HTTP request are sent:

1. Using an identifier of a public collection.

2. Using an identifier of a private collection whose access is authorised for the agent.
3. Using an identifier of a private collection whose access is not authorised for the agent.

The system should perform the desired operation as result of the first and second request and should respond with an “Access denied” error as a result of the third one.

2.1.2 Data collection

For this test, the system should be configured to include both a public and a private collection.

2.1.3 Performance evaluation

The results of the test are evaluated only in terms of correctness. To this end, all steps that are described in the test scenario will be carried out.

2.2 TEST 2: POPULATION WORKFLOW

The objective of this test is to check the functioning of the population workflow. A detailed specification of the population workflow is presented in the ANNEX of this document.

2.2.1 Test scenario

In its simple form, this test scenario consists of starting a single instance of the population workflow and to check that the following conditions hold when its execution is completed:

- If one of the model identifiers serving as input does not exist in the corresponding service, if the specified collection does not exist, or if the input Lynx document is not valid, then the population workflow should end with a business error, and there should not be side effects in the Lynx system.
- If no business error occurs, then the enriched document saved in the LKG and indexed must be a valid RDF Lynx document, and it must contain all the enrichments that are produced by the models specified as input.

These conditions should then be tested with different enrichment configurations and documents (valid and invalid).

Furthermore, to test the behaviour of the system under a stress condition, a workload of several population workflow instances should also be experimented. This test should be repeated with an increasing number of documents, different enrichment configurations, documents of different size and language, and also scaling in and out the microservices owned by the Lynx consortium.

2.2.2 Data collection

The evaluation of the population workflow will be carried out using a collection of documents made up of documents in the four relevant languages in the project (English, German, Spanish and Dutch). Furthermore, we have decided to divide the documents into four different groups, which are described below:

1. Set 1: contains a single short document (approx. 300 words)
2. Set 2: contains a single long document (approx. 2000 words)

3. Set 3: contains 10 short documents (avg. 500 words)
4. Set 4: contains 10 long documents (avg. 3000 words)

A second collection of documents is needed in the scalability scenario, where a bigger number of documents is required to stress the system and verify the scalability of the components.

2.2.3 Performance evaluation

The test's results are evaluated both in terms of correctness (true or false), and of processing speed.

The adopted performance index for the processing speed is the throughput measured in word per seconds. Beyond the infrastructure, the implementations and the horizontal scaling configuration, the throughput depends also on:

- The documents' enrichment configurations. The population workflow can be configured with multiple combinations of enrichment tasks, and, for each requested enrichment task, different enrichment models can have different performances.
- The domain and the language of the documents. Indeed, some enrichment models are faster to execute with documents of certain domain and language.

In general, when the throughput is considered for a workload with a fixed enrichment configuration, and with documents of the same language and domain, it can be used to compare several systems.

3 PILOT USE CASES LEVEL TESTING AND EVALUATION PLAN

3.1 TEST STRATEGY

The Test Strategy presents the approach to the testing of the pilots. The following section (3.2 to 3.4) on Test Requirements for each Use Case describes *what* will be tested; this describes *how* it will be tested.

The main considerations for the test strategy are the techniques to be used and the criteria for knowing when the testing is completed. In addition to the considerations provided for each test below, testing should only be executed using known, controlled databases, in dedicated environments.

The following test strategy is generic in nature and is meant to apply to the requirements list.

3.1.1 Data and Database Integrity Testing

The databases and the database processes should be tested as separate systems. These systems should be tested without the GUI applications (as the interface to the data).

Test Objective:	Ensure Data access methods and processes function properly and without data corruption.
Technique:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invoke each data access method and process, seeding each with valid and invalid data (or requests for data). • Inspect the database to ensure the data has been populated as intended, all database events occurred properly, or review the returned data to ensure that the correct data was retrieved (for the correct reasons)
Completion Criteria:	All database access methods and processes function as designed and without any data corruption.
Special Considerations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testing may require a DBMS development environment or drivers to enter or modify data directly in the databases. • Processes should be invoked manually. • Small or minimally sized databases (limited number of records) should be used to increase the visibility of any non-acceptable events.

3.1.2 Function Testing

Testing of the application should focus on any target requirements that can be traced directly to use cases (or business functions), and business rules. The goals of these tests are to verify proper data acceptance, processing, and retrieval, and the appropriate implementation of the business rules. This type of testing is based upon black box techniques, that is, verifying the application (and its internal processes) by interacting with the application via the GUI and analyzing the output (results). Identified below is an outline of the testing recommended for each application:

Test Objective:	Ensure proper application navigation, data entry, processing, and retrieval.
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Technique:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Execute each use case, use case flow, or function, using valid and invalid data, to verify the following: The expected results occur when valid data is used. The appropriate error / warning messages are displayed when invalid data is used. Each business rule is properly applied.
Completion Criteria:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All planned tests have been executed. All identified defects have been addressed.

3.1.3 User Interface Testing

User Interface testing verifies a user's interaction with the software. The goal of UI Testing is to ensure that the User Interface provides the user with the appropriate access and navigation through the functions of the applications. In addition, UI Testing ensures that the objects within the UI function as expected and conform to corporate and industry standards.

Test Objective:	Verify the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Navigation through the application properly reflects business functions and requirements, including screen to screen, field to field, and use of access methods (tab keys, mouse movements, accelerator keys) Screen objects and characteristics, such as menus, size, position, state, and focus conform to standards.
Technique:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create / modify tests for each screen to verify proper navigation and object states for each application screen and objects.
Completion Criteria:	Each screen successfully verified to remain consistent with benchmark version or within acceptable standard

3.1.4 Performance Testing

Performance testing measures response times, transaction rates, and other time sensitive requirements. The goal of Performance testing is to verify and validate the performance requirements have been achieved. Performance testing is usually executed several times, each using a different "background load" on the system. The initial test should be performed with a "nominal" load, similar to the normal load experienced (or anticipated) on the target system. A second performance test is run using a peak load.

Additionally, Performance tests can be used to profile and tune a system's performance as a function of conditions such as workload or hardware configurations.

NOTE: Transactions below refer to "logical business transactions." These transactions are defined as specific functions that an end user of the system is expected to perform using the application, such as add or modify a given contract.

Test Objective:	Validate System Response time for designated transactions or business functions under the following condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • normal anticipated volume
Technique:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Test Scripts developed for Business Model Testing (System Testing). • Modify data files (to increase the number of transactions) or modify scripts to increase the number of iterations each transaction occurs. • Scripts should be run on one machine (best case to benchmark single user, single transaction) and be repeated with multiple clients (virtual or actual, <i>see special considerations below</i>).
Completion Criteria:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single Transaction / single user: Successful completion of the test scripts without any failures and within the expected / required time allocation (per transaction) • Multiple transactions / multiple users: Successful completion of the test scripts without any failures and within acceptable time allocation.

3.1.5 Security and Access Control Testing

Security and Access Control Testing focus on two key areas of security:

- Application security, including access to the Data or Business Functions, and
- System Security, including logging into / remote access to the system.

Application security ensures that, based upon the desired security, users are restricted to specific functions or are limited in the data that is available to them. For example, everyone may be permitted to enter data and create new accounts, but only managers can delete them. If there is security at the data level, testing ensures that user "type" one can see all customer information, including financial data, however, user two only sees the demographic data for the same client.

System security ensures that only those users granted access to the system are capable of accessing the applications and only through the appropriate gateways.

Test Objective:	Function / Data Security: Verify that users can access only those functions / data for which their user type is provided permissions. System Security: Verify that only those users with access to the system and application(s) are permitted to access them.
Technique:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Function / Data Security: Identify and list each user type and the functions / data each type has permissions for. • Create tests for each user type and verify permission by creating transactions specific to each user type.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modify user type and re-run tests for same users. In each case verify those additional functions / data are correctly available or denied. • System Access (see special considerations below)
Completion Criteria:	For each known user type the appropriate function / data are available and all transactions function as expected and run in prior Application Function tests

3.2 OPENLAWS: CONTRACTS

This Test Plan describes the integration and system tests that will be conducted on the architectural prototype for the Contracts-Use Case. It is assumed that unit testing is already provided.

3.2.1 Requirements for Test

The listing below identifies those items (use cases, functional requirements, non-functional requirements) that have been identified as targets for testing. This list represents *what* will be tested.

Data and Database Integrity Testing

- Verify access to Contract Database
- No data will be stored in the Lynx-System after a contract has been analysed

Function Testing

- Analyse a single contract
- Analyse various contracts
- Archive contract within openlaws system
- Manage contracts
- Visualize single contracts with annotations
- Visualize the data space
- Navigate through the data space
- Search within the data space

User Interface Testing

- Verify ease of navigation through the set of screens.
- Verify sample screens conform to GUI standards.
- The System shall be easy-to-use and shall be appropriate for the target market.

Performance Testing

- Verify response time to access the system.
- Verify response time to analyze a single contract

Security and Access Control Testing

- Verify security through user name and password mechanisms.
- Verify functional security based on user role

3.3 DNV GL: GEOTHERMAL ENERGY

This Test Plan describes the integration and system tests that will be conducted on the architectural prototype for the Geothermal energy Case.

3.3.1 Requirements for Test

The listing below identifies those items (use cases, functional requirements, non-functional requirements) that have been identified as targets for testing. This list represents *what* will be tested.

Data and Database Integrity Testing

- Verify access to Geothermal energy database.
- No data will be stored in the Lynx-System after a user-input-document has been analysed. A user-input-document is generally a PDF document the user uploads / or 'drags and drops' in the drop-zone, for example an RFP

Function Testing

- Analyse a single file: user uploads / drag-drops one PDF
- Visualize single document with annotations
- Annotations have the correct colour to indicate a category
- Semantic search results are presenter in the 'recommender page' per category
- Search results show a 'fingerprint' of terms to indicate it relevancy
- Use can navigate through categories of search results without losing the data
- Use can us global search within the data space (without the file drop-zone)

User Interface Testing

- Verify ease of navigation through the set of screens.
- Verify sample screens conform to GUI standards.
- The System shall be easy-to-use and shall be appropriate for the target market.

Performance Testing

- Verify response time to access the system.
- Verify response time to analyses a single PDF document (approximately 15 pages ~ 1 mb)

Security and Access Control Testing

- Verify security through user name and password mechanisms.
- Verify functional security based on user role

3.4 CUATRECASAS: LABOUR LAW

To black-box test Labour Law use case, we will differentiate between functional and non-functional testing. At this point we have also introduced some acceptance criteria values specially focused on the accuracy level of the trained QADOC Service.

3.4.1 Requirements for Test

The listing below identifies those items (use cases, functional requirements, non-functional requirements) that have been identified as targets for testing. This list represents *what* will be tested.

Data and Database Integrity Testing

- Users, Company and personal settings, and audit/history activity stored in the App Database.
- Documents stored in LKG Private and Public Collections

Functional Testing

Main objective of functional testing is to ensure that the implemented software meets the business needs. To ensure that we are referring to the main functional requirements described in D5.3.

As a short introduction we want to remember our high-level application objective: we are envisioning a system/application where the user submits a legal question regarding labour law and workers' regulations, specifying one or more jurisdictions. The system should then return the most relevant information based on the direct texts of the law, including the following:

- The most precise answer possible (when the question is specific, asking for a value, data and name).
- The paragraph(s) related with the topic/question, where the possible answer appears as part of the text.
- Providing the context by showing the article (and section) from which the paragraph(s) is extracted, showing the number and title, and allowing the user to view the full text of the article and law, which the user should be able to access and download.

Main use case functionalities:

- **The user should be able to upload a document into the LKG.** This document can be MS Word or PDF file, and could be in any of the supported languages of Lynx. This document must be classified with a valid Jurisdiction, valid Language, valid Type of Document. Also, the document has to be classified as Public or Private. If is a private one then additional company parameter should be provided. D5.3 Requirements involved: REQ07
- **The user should be able to specify a subset of documents from his accessible LKG as a document corpora base** to ask labour employment questions later on. This document selection should be done based on some metadata filtering (language, jurisdiction, type of document, company, document name, etc.). The list of individual documents should be provided finally to the QA service; this document list should be managed by the user (based on his own configuration defaults or using the functionality of adding/removing specific documents in the application session, D5.3 Requirements involved: REQ06
- **The user should be able to write some legal questions in natural language, in any of the supported languages. The system will find and retrieve most relevant answers into the previously specified list of documents grouped by jurisdiction.** Results (on any jurisdiction) will be a concrete answer (where is possible) and/or a paragraph or l of paragraphs into the documents

where the possible answer is located. Results list (paragraphs) will be organized by Document > Section > Article, and will be ordered by Accuracy level/Relevance. D5.3 Requirements involved: REQ01, REQ03, REQ08

- **The user should be able to bulk-process list of questions, this list of questions could be uploaded from an excel file or be manually added.** The system should be able to show the results in the application, while also providing the option to generate the results in an Excel file. Requirements involved: REQ11
- **The user should be able to see the relevant information translated into different supported languages.** The system will present the user question translated into the language of any of the selected jurisdictions. The system will present all the results into the different jurisdiction in the user (predefined) language and also has the functionality to translate any answer to any other supported language, at paragraph, article and also document level. D5.3 Requirements involved: REQ01, REQ03, REQ10

Based on these main functionalities and concrete detailed requirements list, a specific test plan will be fulfilled, detailing information about navigation steps, inputs allowed and not allowed, and for each combination the expected results should be described, to evaluate level of accomplishment and quality assurance review.

User Interface Testing

- Verify ease of navigation through the set of screens.
- Verify sample screens conform to GUI standards and Cuatrecasas specific branding requirements.
- Usability and GUI issues will be reported as part of the functional testing verification

Performance Testing

- Verify response time to access the system.
- Verify response time to upload a new document.
- Verify response time to present the list of answers by jurisdiction. [KEY]
- Verify response time to on-demand translation of results (paragraph, article, ...)
- Also performance evaluation and data collection should be reported as part of the functional testing verification

Security and Access Control Testing

- Verify security through username and password mechanisms.
- Verify functional security based on user role
- Verify and ensure logical access control to documents by user and company

3.4.2 Acceptation criteria

Acceptation criteria definition will be necessary to evaluate quality and accuracy in the QADOC Service. At this point we can consider as an acceptable accuracy in our use case:

1. 80% best possible answer in the first result
2. 90% best possible answer into the TOP 3 results

These values have been specified assuming documents created in Spanish and English version and also questions written in any of these languages. Other language combinations and specially working with documents in other languages should be re-evaluated, because they will be very dependent of the final level of Machine Translation service between the other supported languages combination.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The milestone achieved with D5.4 is the definition of the testing and evaluation plan of the Lynx project. The plan is structured in three levels: the microservice level, where microservices are tested as single components, the integration level, in which are tested the functionalities of the Lynx platform consisting of many integrated microservices, and the pilot use-cases level, which comprises all the acceptance tests for the pilot use cases.

In Section 2 of this document we have defined the integration testing plan, which will focus on the population workflow and the private collections.

In Section 3 we have defined the general strategies and the requirements for testing the three different pilot use cases: contracts (openlaws), labour law (Cuatrecasas) and geothermal energy (DNV GL).

The next step in Task 5.4 is putting into practice the tests defined in Section 2 and 3 of this document using the established methodology.

ANNEX: POPULATION WORKFLOW SPECIFICATION

The population workflow is used to enrich documents with Lynx enrichment services, save them in the LKG and index them through the Lynx search engine (Figure 1). It is the only way for Lynx clients to add new documents to the Lynx platform.

The required input parameters of the population workflow are:

- An RDF Lynx document. The Lynx OWL ontology is defined in <http://lynx-project.eu/doc/lkg.ttl>, whereas the SHACL ¹ shapes used for the validation are maintained in <https://gitlab.com/superlynx/doc>.
- An enrichment configuration, which consists of a map from enrichment tasks to model identifiers. An enrichment task is a predefined type of enrichment for a Lynx document while a model identifier is a reference to a specific implementation of an enrichment task. An enrichment task can be deactivated by simply not specifying the corresponding model. An example enrichment configuration represented as a table is shown in Table 1.
- A reference to a Lynx collection. A collection is a group of Lynx documents with a dedicated index. Lynx collections can either public or private.

Figure 1 BPMN 2.0 diagram of the population workflow

Enrichment task	Model identifier
NER	ner-wikinerEn_PER;ner-wikinerEn_LOC;ner-wikinerEn_ORG
Entity Linking	1E14BF84-57A4-0001-1FAB-1AADDDED47C00
Translation to de	smt-99b2f71a-1b3b-418e-bd6b-125f61a53feb
GEO	ner-wikinerEn_LOC

Table 1 A sample enrichment configuration

¹ SHACL is a language for validating RDF graphs against a set of conditions. These conditions are provided as shapes and other constructs expressed in the form of an RDF graph.

REST API

A detailed description of the REST API can be found in the OpenAPI specification of the Lynx Workflow Manager (http://lynx-project.eu/doc/api/yamls/alp_wm.yaml). Furthermore, the Workflow Manager REST API is currently accessible with a user-friendly Swagger UI interface at this link: http://lynx-project.eu/doc/api/alp_wm.html#/LKGP/post_workflows_LKGP

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